

Effectiveness of Sales Promotion Tools on Consumer Buying Behaviour of Sachet Oil in Ado Ekiti Metropolis

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Abstract

The study examined the effectiveness of sales promotional tools on the customer buying behaviour of sachet oil in Ado Ekiti metropolis. Specifically, the study investigated the effect of sales promotion on customer buying behaviour. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of sachet oil consumers in Ado Ekiti. 210 respondents were sampled via random sampling. A primary source through a structured questionnaire was employed. Descriptive statistic through frequency tables was used to analyse the demographic information of the respondents while inferential statistic through regression was used to test the study hypothesis. The study found rebate and discount offers, price pack, contest positively and significant on consumer buying behaviour while coupon was found insignificant on consumer buying behaviour thus concluded that sales promotion positively affects the consumers buying behaviour of sachet oil in Ado-Ekiti metropolis. Therefore, the study recommended that sachet oil manufacturers should pay more attention to the sales promotional tools as a mean to influence customer purchasing behaviour.

Keyword: Promotional Mix, Sales Promotion, Consumer, Consumer Buying Behaviour

1 INTRODUCTION

In the current global business, the influence of sales promotion cannot be ignored in determining the survival of any product. However, sales promotion goes a long way in promoting products and also increases the competitive strength of a firm especially in this intensely competitive environment. Therefore, sales promotion plays a major role in creating awareness particularly on new products and to keep the existing products in the mind of prospective customers. In view of the above fact, sales promotion, as opined by Ahmad, Mehmood, Ahmed, Mustafa, Khan and Yasmeen (2015), enables the customer to buy more and also leads to an impulse purchase, where unplanned for purchase happens due to the promotional techniques. Similarly, sales promotion stands the chances of increasing sales volume and profitability. The business will only continue to exist when its productions are sold in the market. On another hand, the promotion price which is an impermanent price reduction presented to consumers, is a major tool or strategy to influence the behaviour of target customers to increase patronage. Promotional tools tend to notify, convince and remind customers about the product offerings. These offerings need to be presented to attract customers to patronise the product. Sales promotion incentive is one of the major tools in increasing consumer patronage and attracting customers. Therefore, promoting sachet oil out rightly to customers will help influence consumer buying behaviour and can also facilitate unplanned purchases of customers passing by in such an environment.

Jean and Yazdanifard (2015) posited that the price and quality of a product are the two main characteristics that determine a customer's purchasing behaviour. Wholesalers or sales force prefers price reduction, discount, rebate, price pack, coupon premium and other sales promotional tools to promote their products and compete against the rivalry brand instead of spending money on advertisement due to the competitive market environment to reduce cost. In view of this, sachet oil size is another factor to reckon with under-price because the various size is given different prices depending on which of the sizes customer can afford for consumption. As a result, the consumer becomes price sensitive that is consumers are more likely to pay more attention to reducing cost through price and increase their purchasing power when they notice there is a price reduction on the potential products they want to buy. Moreso, an immediate price discount as an effective sales promotion strategy would help in influencing the purchasing behaviour for both rational and non-rational consumers (Liao, Shen, & Chu, 2009). Therefore, this study will be of benefit to the manufacturers, marketers, and sales force of

sachet oil on the need to perfectly understand the behavioural aspect of the consumer in order to exercise the right and most effective promotional strategy to attract prospective customers.

The demanding rate of sachet oil is becoming more alarming recently; sachet oil is a household product that commands high patronage daily because of the product necessity. Sachet oil can be used to fry, cook and perform other functions. Manufacturers are now venturing in to producing sachet oil like king oil, power oil and the likes. However, the variation in size and price of the sachet oil has left the prospective buyers with alternatives. Currently, in Nigeria, where recession is the order of the day, sale promotion is one of the best techniques or tools to increase the market share of power oil products. It is of no doubt that consumer now preferred sachet oil to the former bottled oil however due to the price variation, sizes, and hygienic consumption out of several vegetable oil product available in the market, sachet oil has become more competitive and demanding despite little or relatively low advertisement put in place. Most of the distributors or sales force in Ado-Ekiti now get involved in aggressive promotional means to improve their sales and capture many customers. Previous studies like Neha and Manoj (2013) found that among the various promotional mix elements, sales promotion is the most stimulating variable for quick selling and only a few of the promotional tools were significant in India. Furthermore, studies like Nagadeepa, Selvi and Pushpa (2015) found only discounts and loyalty programme to be significant in India. In view of the above fact, their study will be adapted on sachet in Ado-Ekiti metropolis. Therefore, this study will investigate the effectiveness of sales promotion on consumer buying behaviour towards the purchase of sachet vegetable oil in Ado Ekiti metropolis.

2 Literature Review

Sales promotion concept is a subset of marketing which becomes necessary for this study to dwell on marketing mix discussion before sales promotion. Familmaleki, Aghighi and Hamidi (2015) defined a marketing mix as the specific combination of marketing elements used to achieve objectives and satisfy the target market. It encompasses four major variables, which are product, distribution, promotion and price. Therefore, marketing mix is defined as the set of controllable, tactical marketing techniques such as price, product, place and promotions) that firms combine to produce the response it wants in the target market (Kotler & Armstrong, 2006).

Sales promotion is one of the most important and bewildering promotional tools of modern marketing management. It is bewildering because of its typically tagged effects and also the difficulty of isolating its effect from other elements in the marketing mix. Sales promotion could be referred to as a “catch all” for those short term marketing activities, which act as an incentive to stimulate quick buyers action such as coupons, sweep take, context, premium, free samples, trading stamps. Sales promotion is a segment of the total promotional and communication mix and the term promotion in its broadest sense means to move forward (Bhandari, 2012).

According to Chaharsoughi and Hamdard (2011), Promotion is employed to ensure that consumers are aware of the products that the organization is offering. The promotional mix is the combination of different channels that can be used to pass a message across to the consumers. The researcher posited further that the promotional mix is: advertising, direct marketing public relations and publicity, personal selling, sponsorship and sales promotion. However, one of the most important promotional mixes is sales promotion. In view of this, sales promotion is action focused marketing events whose purpose is to have a direct impact on the behaviour of the consumers due to personal interaction or face to face conversation between both sales force and customers in generating genuine information from the source. Montany, Chernatony and Buil (2011) are of the opinion that gift promotion is more preferable by the consumers than price discounts. For example, consumers prefer to receive gifts that have high equity as the products they have purchased than receiving a price discount. Mughal, Mehmood, Mohi-uddeen and Ahmad (2015) opines that promotion is an instrument used by the retailers or manufacturers to attract consumers to purchase more of the product. The result of the sales promotion is the used of high quantity stock, appealing to many new customers and more increase in sales.

Chandon, Wansink, and Laurent (2000) indicated that sales promotion might be gorgeous for well promotion prone consumers for reasons beyond price savings. Many consumers change

brands so that they could receive greater deals that replicate and build up their smart buyer self-perception, and these consumers are favourably promotion prone, these consumers make an attempt to try a new product or service that have been promoted. For an example, a decrease in price for a limited period to attract more new consumers is referred to as price promotion. Sales promotion means any activity that is utilized by the producer to give confidence the trade (retailer, wholesaler, or network associates) as well as make customers purchase a brand and boost up a sales force to assertively sell it. Lehman and Winer (2002) defined sales promotion as special offers that essentially aim to stimulate demand for a product. Defining the term sales promotion is rather difficult for the presence of multiple relating techniques and tactics and that sales promotion is a tool to achieve the company's marketing communication objectives (Familmaleki, Aghighi & Hamidi, 2015).

When the extra produce contains without any additional price, customers could be convinced to purchase such produce but if the consumers have the sense that their money can be kept with this deal, the bonus packages inspire the consumers to purchase the produce (Percy, Rossiter & Elliott 2001). The bonus packs liked by producers or manufacturers because it should increase the product trial, switching a product and forcing stores to stock products. This technique of promotion would be very useful to the manufacturer because it should help the retailers to clear the stock more hastily as contrast price promotion (Li, Sun & Wang, 2007). A price reduction which is received by a customer after the purchase has been made is termed as rebate Discount is the offer when products are sold at a price lower than the original price Retailers provide consumers a reduced price scheme that is marked directly on the package of two or more products by the marketer. Here a number of products are bundled together at the price of one or at discounted rates such as 'Buy-Two-get-one- free (Nagadeepa, Selvi & Pushpa, 2015).

Salvi (2013) observed that the discount and price off scheme induced the customers to visit the store and influenced their purchase decision. And also buy one get one free has been found effective in their purchase decision. Brassington and Pttitt (2000) provide a revised definition for sales promotions: 'a range of marketing techniques designed within a strategic marketing framework, to add extra value to a product or service over and above the "normal" offering in order to achieve specific sales and marketing objectives, this extra value may be a short term tactical nature or it may be part of a longer-term franchise building program. Neha and Manoj (2013) categorised sales promotion into consumer sales promotion and trade sales promotion, where consumer sales promotion incorporates a variety of short-term promotional techniques designed to induce customers to respond in some way. It is intended to enhance the value of a product either by reducing costs or adding benefits.

osman, Chan and Foon (2011) asserted that considering buying behaviour, consumers usually have endless demand to fulfil their needs and satisfaction to obtain something new or better as every individual has their own behaviour attitude and thought while choosing products services and making a purchase decision. According to Smelser and Baltes (2001), daily life activities are dominated by purchasing behaviour and also an experience gained from personal contact or interaction with consumers. Consumers are the ultimate end user of a product. They keep the production cycle moving. The role of Consumers is so important in determining the economic system of any nation. Thus, the effectiveness of demand for goods produced in certain nations majorly controlled and determined by consumers in which failure to consume such produce will have an adverse effect on the growth and development of such an economy (Ampofo, 2014). Consumers request for diverse commodities based on their taste and preference for them. Aggressive promotions of goods influence consumers' purchase behaviour. However, consumers are known to be logical with regard to their purchases, wanting to maximize their satisfaction when it comes to buyer goods.

Consequently, consumer behaviour study refers to how an individual or groups select, purchase, use or dispose of products, services ideas, or experience to suit their need and desires. The consumer environment influences how the consumer feels consider and act. The environmental features are environmental scanning, promotion, packaging, price and product appearance etc. (Paul & Jerry, 2005). According to Papanastassiu and Rouhani (2006), behaviour can be analyzed in different ways, by offering lower prices, better service and good quality. Consumer behaviour mainly sheds light on how consumers decide to spend their various resources like time and money on various products so as to meet their daily needs (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2004). Therefore, the price,

product packaging, quality and other promotional means are strategies to capture customers. In view of the above, sales promotion has a far reaching effect on influencing customer attitude towards purchases of goods.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Planned Behaviour Theory will underpin this study. However, according to the theory, the behaviour may be modified by sales promotion stimuli, which change beliefs, attitudes and eventual intentions and behaviour. Therefore, if the intervention influences customers, it changes the customer's intentions and eventually changes customer's behaviour.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

Neha and Manoj (2013) investigated the impact of sales promotion tools on consumer's purchase decisions towards a good white refrigerator at Durg and Bhilai Region of CG, India. The study employed a descriptive research design through a structured questionnaire while 109 respondents were sampled convenience sampling. Data generated were analysed using multiple regression techniques. The result showed that among the various sales promotion tools, offer, premium and contest are the most influencing variables for consumer purchase decisions while price pack and rebate are found insignificant on the consumer purchase decision.

Nagadeepa, Selvi and Pushpa (2015) examined the impact of sale promotion techniques on consumers' impulse buying behaviour towards apparel at Bangalore. Five important sales promotion techniques namely, Rebate & Discount offer, Coupon, Loyalty Programs, Price Packs and Contests, are considered in the study. A self-administered questionnaire is administered and a total of 110 respondents are interviewed with it. The generated data is analyzed using regression analysis and it is found that Rebates and Discount offer and Loyalty programs significantly affect impulse buying behaviour while coupon, price pack and the contest does not significantly affect impulse buying behaviour at Bangalore. The study recommended that marketers should focus on the remaining sales promotion tools to make them a perfect promoting strategy to promote their products.

Suresh, Anandanatarajan and Sritharan (2015) evaluated the effect of sales promotion tools on customer purchase decisions with special reference camera products at Chennai, Tamilnadu. The study data was collected through a convenience sampling of 109 respondents through a descriptive research design. Descriptive through frequency tables and percentages were employed while the hypothesis was tested using multiple regression analysis. The study found that three of the constructs measured (offer, premium and contest) significantly influences a consumer purchase decision while the other two, which are rebate and price pack has no significant effect on the consumer purchase decision. Therefore, from the review of the aforementioned literature above, it is discovered that their findings are not stable and that different sales promotion factors are significant in different directions and that the contradictory result has provided a reasonable gap for further studies to dwell on. In view of this, the effort will be geared towards investigating the effect of sales promotion on consumer buying behaviour with reference to sachet oil in Ado-Ekiti metropolis.

3 METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey. The primary source through a well-structured questionnaire is employed to gather information from the target respondent of sachet oil consumers in Ado Ekiti. The population for this study was derived from the entire population of people in Ado Ekiti. Three major markets (Ewi Market, Bisi Egbeyemi Market and Shasha Market) will be sampled where 70 respondents were randomly sampled in each market, bringing the total to 210 due to the huge number of daily market patronage in the three markets. This study only employs discount and rebate, coupon, contest and price pack as the proxy of sales promotion on consumer buying behaviour. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed using SPSS 2.0 version. Descriptive statistic through a simple percentage and frequency table was employed while inferential statistic through regression analysis was used test the study hypothesis.

4 RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Presentation of Respondents' Demographic Data

A discussion of findings is presented based on the specific objectives of the study. 210 respondents were sampled, 180 questionnaires were filled and returned which represented an 85.7% response rate. This implies that the response rate to the information needed for this study is adequate for data analysis.

Table 1 Sex Distribution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	72	40.0	40.0	40.0
Valid Female	108	60.0	60.0	100.0
Total	180	100.0	100.0	

From the sex distribution, as indicated in table 1, it was indicated that the male distribution was 72 (40.0%), while the female was 108 (60.0%). Therefore, female customers are more than the male customers. However, this implied that female customers are more vibrant and visit the market most compared to the male counterpart.

Table 2 Mode of Patronage Distribution

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Daily	30	16.6	16.6	16.6
Valid Weekly	91	50.6	50.6	67.2
Valid Monthly	47	26.1	26.1	93.3
Valid Yearly	12	6.7	6.7	100.0
Total	180	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.4 shows that (30) 16.6% of the respondents patronises sachet oil daily, (91) 50.6% of the respondents patronises sachet oil weekly, (47) 26.1% of the respondents patronises sachet oil monthly while (12) 6.7% of the respondents patronises sachet oil yearly thus implies that majority of the respondent surveyed patronises sachet oil daily. This implied that sachet oil necessity that is highly consumed and demanded.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

Table 3: Regression Results of Sales Promotion on Consumer Buying Behaviour

Model	R	R ²	Adj R ²	B	Std. Error	T value	P Value	Remark
	.820	.672	.658					
Rebate and Discount Offer				.405	.093	4.629	.000	Sig
Coupon				.183	.065	1.848	.066	Not Sig
Price Pack				.422	.089	5.986	.000	Sig
Contest				.394	.097	3.307	.000	Sig
Constant				1.873	.279	4.211	.000	Sig
F- Cal 48.680								
F-Tab 1.645								

Source: Data Analysis, 2019

From Table 3, sales promotion scores on four variables which are the rebate and discount offer, coupon, price pack and contest. The R (Regression Coefficient) of sales promotion gives a positive value of 0.820; this indicated that sales promotion has a very strong significant effect on consumer buying behaviour of sachet oil. The R² is a portion of the total variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the variation in the independent variables. From the results obtained, R² is equal to 0.672, this implies that sales promotion brought about 67.2% variance in consumer buying behaviour of sachet oil in Ado-Ekiti metropolis, this is further proven by the adjusted R² that shows the goodness of fit of the model which gives a value of 0.658, implying that when all errors are corrected and adjustments are made the model can only account for 65.8% of sales promotion in the surveyed market.

The unstandardized β co-efficient, rebate and discount offer gives a positive value of 0.405 with $t= 4.629$ and ($P= .000 < 0.05$). This result showed that rebate and discount offer has a positive effect on consumer buying behaviour therefore, It was found significant. This means that respondents' reason for consumer buying behaviour is strongly influenced by rebate and discount offer thus implied that selling at a lower price than the original price will surely influence consumer buying behaviour. Furthermore, the unstandardized β co-efficient of coupon gives a positive value of 0.183 with $t= 1.848$ and ($P= .066 < 0.05$). This result showed that coupon has a positive effect on consumer buying behaviour but found insignificant. This means that respondents' reason for consumer buying behaviour is not influenced by coupon. The unstandardized β co-efficient of price pack gives a positive value of 0.422 with $t= 5.986$ and ($P= .000 < 0.05$). This result showed that the price pack has a positive effect on consumer buying behaviour therefore, It was found significant. This means that respondents' reason for consumer behaviour is strongly influenced by price pack, as indicated in table 3. The unstandardized β co-efficient of contest gives a positive value of 0.394 with $t= 3.307$ and ($P= .000 < 0.05$). This result showed that contest has a positive effect on consumer buying behaviour. Therefore, It was found significant. This means that respondents' reason for consumer buying behaviour is influenced by contest as depicted from table 3 thus implied that organising lucky draw influences consumer buying behaviour. This study result contradicts the study of Neha and Manoj (2013) and Negadeepa, Selvi and Pushpa (2015) in India who only found a few of their constructs positive. However, the study is in accordance with reviewed theories that found sales promotion influential on consumer buying behaviour.

The F-test is used to test the overall significance of a model by comparing the F calculated with the F tabulated of each determinant, the comparison is made in Table 3. The table shows that the calculated values of F distribution give values greater than the F tabulated. Hence, we accept alternate hypotheses and reject null hypotheses. Therefore, sales promotion has a significant effect on consumer buying behaviour.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the effectiveness of sales promotion on consumer buying behaviour of sachet oil in Ado-Ekiti metropolis. According to the obtained result, rebate and discount offer, coupon, price pack and contest were used to proxy sales promotion and the explanatory variable has a very strong effect on consumer buying behaviour. Sales promotion construct measured found except coupon that has positive value but has no significant effect on consumer buying behaviour all at 0.05 level of significance. Price pack is found to have the most significant value than other measures on consumer buying behaviour thus implied that sales promotion is positively related to the consumer buying behaviour of sachet oil in Ado-Ekiti metropolis.

In view of the above findings, it is recommended that sachet oil manufacturers and other actors on the distribution chain should pay proper attention to sales promotion as a tool to increase sales particularly in rural and urban markets, to make products available to customers. Quality and proper packaging are also very important in communicating and promoting the product to consumers. Therefore, it is necessary to set a packaging standard and to implement a strategy that protects and promotes sachet oil to gain more competitive advantage. Finally, it is recommended that marketers and manufacturers should not consider only price pack and discount offer as the sole means of promoting a product but should also employ other dimensions of sales promotion in building solid promotional strategy while marketing their product to boost competition and increase market share in the long run.

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